

ZAMONAVIY O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGI, ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIGI VA TIL TA‘LIMINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI

mavzusidagi respublika
ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,**

Tilshunos olim **Abdullayev Jumanazar Xudoyberdiyevichning** 70 yilligiga
bag‘ishlangan

**“ZAMONAVIY O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGI,
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2026-yil 05-may

GULISTON – 2026

Zamonaviy o‘zbek tilshunosligi, adabiyotshunosligi va til ta’limining dolzarb muammolari [Matn]: to‘plam. – Guliston, 2026. – 476 b.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 20-oktabrdagi “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PF-6084-sonli Farmoniga muvofiq “2020-2030-yillarda o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi”da belgilangan vazifalarning ijrosini ta’minlash maqsadida **Guliston davlat universitetida 2026-yil 05-may kuni** Tilshunos olim **Abdullayev Jumanazar Xudoyberdiyevichning** 70 yilligiga bag‘ishlab o‘tkazilgan “**ZAMONAVIY O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGI, ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIGI VA TIL TA’LIMINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI**” mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. Anjuman zamonaviy tilshunoslikning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzulari va amaliy masalalariga doir uslubiy ishlanmalarni aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

erishadi, garchi baliqning faqat boshi va dumi qolgan bo'lsa ham. Men bu asardan uchta asosiy saboq oldim: **sabr, jasorat va do'stlik**. Santyago jasur inson edi – u qulaylikdan ko'ra sarguzashtni tanladi. Rostini aytsam, uning yo'li har doim ham oqilona emasdek tuyuladi, lekin u bizga sharaf va qadr-qimmatning naqadar muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Muallif Ernest Hemingway orqali berilgan asosiy xabar — bu sinovlarga qarshi turish va o'zini hurmat qilishdir. Santyago juda sabrli inson hamdir. U katta baliq bilan og'ir kurash olib borsa-da, taslim bo'lmaydi. Bu esa sabr oxir-oqibat qoniqish va baxt keltirishini anglatadi. Hayotda ko'plab qiyinchiliklarga duch kelamiz va ko'pincha taslim bo'lamiz. Santyagoning hayoti esa bizni umidsizlikka tushmaslikka undaydi. Shuningdek, Santyago va Manolin o'rtasidagi do'stlik juda muhim. Zamonaviy jamiyatda ishonch va hurmatni saqlash qiyin, ammo Manolin obrazi bizga sadoqat va ishonchning qadrini eslatadi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, bu asarni o'qishni tavsiya qilaman. U nafaqat mashhur va qiziqarli, balki chuqur ma'naviy saboqlarga boy. Santyagoning mashhur so'zi hanuzgacha ruhlantiradi: *“Insonni yo‘q qilish mumkin, lekin uni yengib bo‘lmaydi.”*

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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PRAGMALINGUISTICS AS THE EVOLUTION OF A CONCEPT AND A SUBJECT OF RESEARCH

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Abstract. This article explores the origins and development of linguistic pragmatics as an independent field within semiotics and linguistics. The article also, highlights the interdisciplinary nature of pragmalinguistics, which emerged at the intersection of linguistics, psycholinguistics, and philosophy. Special attention is given to the role of context, communicative intentions, and the interaction between speaker and listener in shaping meaning.

Key words: pragmalinguistics, semiotics, speaker's intention, communication, linguistic signs in speech.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola semiotika va tilshunoslikning mustaqil sohasi sifatida pragmalingvistikaning kelib chiqishi va rivojlanishini o'rganadi. Shuningdek, maqolada tilshunoslik, psixolingvistika va falsafa chorrahasida paydo bo'lgan pragmalingvistikaning fanlararo xususiyati yoritilgan. Ma'noni shakllantirishda kontekst, kommunikativ niyatlar, so'zlovchi va tinglovchi o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmalingvistika, semiotika, so'zlovchi niyati, muloqot, nutqdagi lingvistik belgilar.

The term “pragmatics” (from the Greek *πράγμα* – “business”, “action”) was introduced into science at the end of the 1930s by C. W. Morris, the founder of semiotics – the general theory of signs. The identification and formation of pragmatics as a field of research began thanks to the ideas of C. S. Peirce, which Morris followed and divided semiotics into semantics - the study of the relationship of signs to objects, syntactics - the study of inter-sign relations, and pragmatics - the study of the relationship of signs to speakers. Thus, pragmatics studies the functioning of signs in real communication processes. C. Morris writes:

«Since the interpreters of most (and perhaps all) signs are living organisms, a sufficient characteristic of pragmatics would be to indicate that it deals with the biotic aspects of semiotics, in other words, with all the psychological, biological and sociological phenomena that are observed in the functioning of signs».[6.C. 63]. Before the irrevocable separation of linguistic pragmatics into a separate branch of research, it was noted that pragmatics does not have clear boundaries; it was understood as “an area of research in semiotics and linguistics in which the functioning of linguistic signs in speech is studied” [3.C. 95]. The problems that were studied within its framework included those that are interconnected with the communicating subject, the recipient, and their interaction during communication.

The same problems arose equally as a subject of study in the field of psycholinguistics. It was understood as "the science that studies the processes of speech production, as well as the perception and development of speech in their relationship to the language system." At the same time, the subject of its research, the said science deepened, in connection with close attention to the individual as a native speaker of the language and thanks to the gravitation towards the analysis of language as a dynamic structure within the framework of speech activity (speech behavior) of a given individual, which originated as one of the “daughter” branches of the psychological theory of activity described by A.N. Leontiev [5.p.21].

Over time, the attention of scientists shifts from the problems of language functioning to the problems of the autonomy of linguistic means from those who speak this language.

Thus, pragmalinguistics is a relatively new field of knowledge at the intersection of linguistics, psychology, and philosophy. It is a branch of contemporary pragmatics and can be understood as a linguistic section of pragmatics or as a pragmatic aspect of linguistics. Sometimes it is referred to as linguistic pragmatics [1, p. 26].

Thus, according to I.P. Susov, the field of pragmalinguistics is linguistics, which establishes connections between lexical units and the context in which they are used. Context should be understood as "...a specific communicative-pragmatic space" that determines the interaction between speaker and listener, writer and reader. It is also worth noting that such a communicative-pragmatic space can be characterized by the place and time of the act of communication [7, p. 119].

Further in the work of Yu. S. Stepanov we find the position that pragmalinguistics is a science that studies the most optimal choice of linguistic means that ensure the success of the act of communication and the establishment of stable communicative connections in the process of verbal communication.

It should also be noted that pragmatic linguistics is interested in the problem of verbal influence between participants in communication. Participants directly influence each other during communication, thereby realizing their plans and achieving their goals and desired results. The goals pursued by the participants can be, according to G.G. Matveeva, immediate, or direct, indirect and hidden. At the moment of communication, the active participant in the dialogue plays the role not of some idealized, abstract figure with all its inherent psychological and social characteristics, but as a person, demonstrating one or more of its own social functions and psychological traits depending on the real environment in which the interaction takes place. [2. p. 49].

At the same time, to interpret a remark, one must pay attention to the identity of the message's addressee, that is, the other participant in the dialogue. The addressee of the message presents themselves in one of their social functions during the interaction. Consequently, the statement must be perceived with an emphasis on these specific parameters, and for the productive implementation of speech interaction it is important that the parameters of the initiator of the message and its addressee are interconnected.

For a correct interpretation of a speech act, one should pay attention to the personal meaning embedded in the speech message by the initiator, taking into account the circumstances of communication. The description of the subject of this science is based on the concept of linguopragmatics as a field of linguistics that studies the connections between signs and the person who forms, receives and analyzes them.

To summarize, linguistic pragmatics is the science that studies the optimal choice of linguistic means, whose functions are:

1. reflecting the speaker's intention;
2. clearly reproducing the contextual meaning of an utterance;
3. mentally defining the unexpressed, which is regulated by the volume of general knowledge.

In linguistics, the term "pragmatics" is not limited to the pragmatic meanings of linguistic units. This term is much broader and encompasses tasks that are inextricably linked to the varying levels of understanding and comprehension of linguistic units and speech productions by participants in the communicative process.

The latter are interpreted differently by participants in the communication process. This can be explained by the fact that people participating in the communicative act possess different linguistic and non-linguistic experiences compared to one another [4. p. 102].

From the point of view of V. N. Komissarov, pragmatics represents the impact on the process and result of translation of the requirements to reproduce the pragmatic potential of the original and attempts to ensure the expected and desired influence on the recipient of information

It should be noted that, in accordance with the definition put forward by V.N. Komissarov, it is possible to define a chain of processes that are in a sequential order and ultimately imply a certain result. [8. p.336].

Taking this sequence into account – from recreating the pragmatic potential of the original text to producing the intended impact on the translation recipient during communication, and finally to the reader's comprehension and interpretation of the translated message – we can trace the full cycle of how pragmatic meaning is transmitted. Based on this definition, it should be noted that the scope of pragmatics covers a broad range of issues:

1. Study of the relationship between the linguistic sign and its decoders (communicator and recipient);
2. Study of the impact of context and secondary extralinguistic factors on dialogue participants;
3. Selecting the most effective linguistic means to increase the effectiveness of communicators' influence on each other;
4. Analyzing the implementation of the initiator's intentions in speech acts.

Linguistic pragmatics is a science that studies the most optimal choice of language means, the functions of which are the reflection of the speaker's intention, the clear reproduction of the contextual meaning of the utterance, the mental definition of the unexpressed, which is regulated by the volume of general knowledge.

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MIR TAMIM ANSARYNING “DESTINY DISRUPTED” ASARIDA ISLOM DUNYOSI TARIXINING MUQOBIL TALQINI: TARIXIY VA MADANIY TAHLIL

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada afg‘on-amerikalik yozuvchi va tarixshunos Tamim Ansary ning *Destiny Disrupted: A History of the World Through Islamic Eyes* asari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi dunyo tarixini Islom sivilizatsiyasi nuqtai nazaridan talqin qilish jarayonini o‘rganishdan iborat. Maqolada asarning tarixiy konsepsiyasi, madaniy va sivilizatsion yondashuvi hamda G‘arb markaziy tarixshunosligiga nisbatan muqobil narrativ yaratish jarayoni tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, asar zamonaviy tarixshunoslikdagi o‘rni hamda tarixiy identitet masalalariga ta’siri ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot davomida tarixshunos olimlar va adabiy tanqidchilar fikrlariga ham murojaat qilinadi. Natijada Ansary asari global tarixni tushunishda muhim ilmiy manba ekanligi aniqlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Islom sivilizatsiyasi, global tarix, tarixiy narrativ, diaspora adabiyoti, madaniy identitet, Sharq va G‘arb munosabatlari, tarixiy tafsir.

Abstract. This article analyzes the work *Destiny Disrupted: A History of the World Through Islamic Eyes* by Afghan-American writer and historian Tamim Ansary from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The main goal of the study is to study the process of interpreting world history from the perspective of Islamic civilization. The article analyzes the historical concept of the work, its cultural and civilizational